

SOCLIMPACT

Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways in EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond

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Work Package 4:

Modelling climate shocks and biophysical impacts

Deliverable 4.1. Report on climatic databases to be used to quantify indicators in the impact chains.

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1 Abstract

In this report we present a catalogue of available data resources for different climate variables needed in the framework of SOCLIMPACT project. This compilation is organized by region to ease the data finding. Then we put the sources for atmospheric data (present and future) and marine data (present and future), referring to common tables that can be found at the end for more details. In each table it is described the variable, the type of data (observational, model or reanalysis), the name of the dataset and the reference to the corresponding table. It has to be noted that data at meteorological and oceanic stations provided by national meteorological services is probably also available. However, the access to data is not straightforward and in most cases a special request is needed to get it. Thus, we have decided to not explicitly include the list here for simplicity. In case that data became necessary, WP4 partners, in collaboration with local working groups could try to get access to those data. At a later stage, this document will be updated to include sources of information for the indicators required by WP3, WP5 and WP6.

As an introductory section we include some plots to show the spatial resolution of typical products. This is done for 4 different spatial resolutions ranging from 1° , typical of global models, to $1/12^\circ$, typical of regional products. We include the figures for three different islands as an illustrative example.

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2 Introduction

The SOCLIMPACT Project aims to conduct an indicator-based assessment of climate-change impacts on selected islands that are characterized by different spatial extension, geographical location and climate, as well as by different economies. In this document, the term indicator refers to the individual components of a synthetic, composite index that simplifies a number of complex and interacting parameters. The diverse parameters that need to be accounted for are, in general, the diverse data types that need to be combined into a form that is more easily understood and used (i.e. as a management tool) in contexts that can be very far from those in and for which the data were originally produced. The development of the indices must clearly progress across sequential stages, from the selection of indicators, the normalization of indicators to a common unitless scale for comparability and commensurability, and their final aggregation into a meaningful index ¹.

In this framework, WP4 is responsible for providing a quantitative, geo-located, evaluation of the climate-related hazards identified in WP3, which, together with exposure and vulnerability, represent the risk component of the sectorial Impact Chains selected within the Project as the most interesting for the economies of insular areas. WP4 is also in charge of computing the related indicators.

The evaluation and review activities to be carried out in Task 4.1 are oriented towards the final goal of computing Climate Change Impact Indicators (CCIIs) that are relevant to the project's purposes, whose definition has indeed been the object of a long-standing discussion among experts. As a matter of fact, the compilation, provision, and update of a complete and readily available dataset, either global or regional, is a very difficult task, due to both data availability and specific application requirements. For this reason, the identification of the indicators to be used within SOCLIMPACT is to be carried out in close collaboration with other WPs. Part of the efforts of participants have therefore been, and will continue to be, devoted to knowledge sharing among the researchers from different fields that are involved in the project. The necessity to develop common views on how to use climate information to produce significant and robust impact indicators has significantly delayed the progress of WP4. This is because it was decided to wait for the definition of the Impact Chains in WP3 and for the needs of WP5 and WP6 before devoting time to the computation of indicators that might then prove of little or no significance.

In the case of maritime transport, the modeling of impacts will be done on the supply side, which is why it is necessary to work with experts to discern the way in which climatic variables affect the production function of maritime transport services. For example, if we are told that a port must remain closed, or limit its activity, when the height of the waves or the speed of the winds exceeds certain thresholds, we must request that the climate models project the percentage of days per year that is expected. exceed these thresholds of wind and waves. This information will be incorporated into the production function to estimate the effect on the economy of maritime transport.

¹ Nguyen, T. T. X., Bonetti, J., Rogers, K. & Woodroffe, C. D. (2016). Indicator-based assessment of climate-change impacts on coasts: a review of concepts, methodological approaches and vulnerability indices. *Ocean and Coastal Management*, 123 18-43

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In the case of aquaculture, the impacts to be modeled are also entirely on the supply side, but in this case, the reduction of productivity depends not only on the effects on the infrastructure, but also on the biology of the species (induced by changes in water temperature, acidification, etc.). Again, the experts must give us the key to translate the crude climate predictions into useful indicators (wind and wave thresholds, CO₂ concentrations, etc.) ... to estimate the economic effects.

In the case of energy demand chains and all tourism chains, the estimates of the impacts of the CC will be carried out exclusively on the demand side. Again, we must confirm with experts and consumers (tourists and residents) the best way to express climate information (indicators) to make predictions about the demand for energy and tourism, for each of the study territories. In addition, although changes in energy demand are directly related to climate variables, in the case of some tourism ICs, the relationship between climate and tourism demand is mediated by the form and intensity with which climate changes affect the ecosystem services on which demand depends on (beaches, marine and terrestrial biodiversity, etc).

For these reasons, this D4.1 focuses mainly on climate data availability from which the indicators required by the other WPs will be produced in the near future and reported in deliverable D4.3 (*"Atlases of newly developed indexes and indicators to estimate climate-related vulnerabilities for the islands of interest, under different climate scenarios"*). At the date this version of D4.1 has been produced, the different sector modelling teams (SMTs) have already selected the Climate Change Impact Indicators (CCIIs) that will be used in the operationalization of the impact chains. These are reported in Section 9.

3 Database overview

Climate projections critically rely on the availability of large ensembles of numerical simulations that guarantee the robustness and accuracy of predicted fields. The following figures synthesize the current situation for the areas of interest in SOCLIMPACT, by reporting the approximate number of atmospheric simulations (ordinate axis) performed over the different regions, for different resolutions (abscissa) and scenarios (color).

The black line corresponds to evaluation runs, the violet line to historical simulations, the light blue line to RCP 4.5, the green line to RCP 8.5, the red line to RCP 2.6.

The Mediterranean region is reasonably covered, especially at low (≈ 50 km) and high (≈ 10 km) resolution, although global simulations have probably too coarse a resolution to be effectively representative. The bulk of the available simulations in these cases come from the EURO-CORDEX database, which also covers the Baltic domain.

Macaronesia and Central America should rely mostly on global databases, as few higher resolution experiments have been performed by individual research institutions, in general not as part of international programmes.

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The situation for the ocean component is even worse, as mostly global simulations are in fact available (103 historical, 79 RCP 4.5, 64 RCP 8.5), which cannot correctly represent the Mediterranean (where a few isolated higher resolution runs have been performed within the Med-CORDEX Programme), and which can only provide information on the large scale circulation features for other domains. On the other hand, data for the Baltic Islands could be provided by the long standing BALTEX Programme. Simulations of wave parameters are also scarce.

As it is not feasible to increment the size of the ensemble of model simulations within the duration of the SOCLIMPACT Project, it is apparent that close collaboration with stakeholders and local meteorological centres will be necessary to extract relevant and effective information even from the coarser experiments.

4 Product resolution

As a guide for users not familiar with model resolution we include here some synthetic information that can help to visualize the spatial resolution of models compared to the islands surface (sections 3.1-3.3). Also, we include a table that summarizes the geographical extension of the islands considered in SOCLIMPACT, together with approximate cell dimensions for typical model resolutions.

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Approximate reference resolutions (lat x lon) at latitude 40N	
$1^\circ \times 1^\circ \approx 111 \text{ km} \times 85 \text{ km} > 9435 \text{ km}^2$ $1/2^\circ \times 1/2^\circ \approx 55 \text{ km} \times 43 \text{ km} > 2365 \text{ km}^2$ $1/4^\circ \approx 28 \text{ km} \times 21 \text{ km} > 588 \text{ km}^2$ $1/8^\circ \approx 14 \text{ km} \times 11 \text{ km} > 154 \text{ km}^2$ $1/12^\circ \approx 9 \text{ km} \times 7 \text{ km} > 63 \text{ km}^2$	
Island	Individual islands of the archipelago
Cyprus <i>Total Area: 9.251 km²</i> <i>Maximum WE length: 195 km</i> <i>Maximum NS length: 82 km</i>	
Balearic Archipelago <i>Total Area: 4.992 km²</i> <i>Maximum WE length: 220 km</i>	Mallorca – <i>Area: 3640 km²</i> Menorca – <i>Area: 668 km²</i> Ibiza – <i>Area: 571 km²</i> Formentera – <i>Area: 83 km²</i> Cabrera – <i>Area: 16 km²</i>
Corsica <i>Total Area: 8680 km²</i> <i>Maximum WE length: 83 km</i> <i>Maximum NS length: 183 km</i>	
Sardinia <i>Total Area: 24.090 km²</i> <i>Maximum WE length: 145 km</i> <i>Maximum NS length: 270 km</i>	
German Baltic Islands <i>Total Area: 1592 km²</i> (but part of Usedom- 72 km ² - is in Poland)	Rügen – <i>Area: 926 km²</i> Usedom – <i>Area: 445 km²</i> Fehmarn – <i>Area: 185 km²</i> Poel – <i>Area: 36 km²</i>
Sicily <i>Total Area: 25.711 km²</i> <i>Maximum WE length: 288 km</i> <i>Maximum NS length: 188 km</i>	
Malta Archipelago <i>Total Area: 316 km²</i>	Malta – <i>Area: 246 km²</i> Gozo – <i>Area: 67 km²</i>
Crete <i>Total Area: 8.336 km²</i> <i>Maximum WE length: 260 km</i> <i>Maximum NS length: 12-60 km</i>	
Canary Archipelago <i>Total Area: 7.493 km²</i>	Tenerife – <i>Area: 2034 km²</i> Fuerteventura – <i>Area: 1660 km²</i>

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<p><i>Maximum WE length: 485 km</i></p>	<p>Gran Canaria– <i>Area:1560 km²</i> Lanzarote– <i>Area:846 km²</i> La Palma– <i>Area:708 km²</i> La Gomera– <i>Area:370 km²</i> El Hierro– <i>Area:269 km²</i></p>
<p>Azores Archipelago <i>Total Area: 2.346 km²</i> <i>Length in the NW-SE direction: 600 km</i></p>	<p>São Miguel– <i>Area:744,55 km²</i> Pico– <i>Area:449,2 km²</i> <i>(46,2 km × 15,8 km)</i> Terceira– <i>Area:396,75 km²</i> <i>(29 km x 17,5 km)</i> São Jorge– <i>Area:243,9 km²</i> <i>(54 km x 6,9 km)</i> Faial– <i>Area:173 km²</i> Flores– <i>Area:143 km²</i> <i>(16,7 km x 12,3 km)</i> Santa Maria – <i>Area: 96,89 km²</i> Graciosa– <i>Area:60,7 km²</i> Corvo– <i>Area:17 km²</i></p>
<p>Madeira Archipelago <i>Total Area: 801 km²</i></p>	<p>Madeira– <i>Area:741km²</i> Porto Santo– <i>Area:42,48km²</i></p>
<p>French West-Indies <i>Total Area: 2804 km²</i> <i>Length of the whole archipelago (including non-EU islands) in the NW-SE direction: 3200 km</i></p>	<p>Guadalupa – <i>Area:1628 km²</i> Martinica – <i>Area:1102 km²</i> <i>(70 km x 30 km)</i> Saint-Martin– <i>Area:53 km²</i> Saint-Barthélemy– <i>Area:21km²</i> Les Saintes – <i>Area:13 km²</i> Marie-Galante– <i>Area:170.5 km²</i> La Désirade – <i>Area:21km²</i> <i>(2 km x 11 km)</i></p>

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4.1 Canary Islands

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4.3 Balearic Islands

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5 Mediterranean

5.1 Atmosphere

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 1
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	E-OBS	Table 6
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	Safran - France	Table 7
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	Safran - Spain	Table 8
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEXAtmosphere Ensemble	Table 15
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	E-OBS	Table 6
Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	Safran - France	Table 7
Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	Safran - Spain	Table 8
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Atmosphere Ensemble	Table 15
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 15
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEXAtmosphere Ensemble	Table 15
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18

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Soil Moisture (daily)	Obs	ESA-CCI	
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 15
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 15
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 15
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 15
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 15
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18

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Soil Moisture (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 15
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18

5.2 Ocean

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 3
3D Temperature (monthly)	Obs	MedHYMAP	Table 10
3D Temperature (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Temperature (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	Mercator	Table 25
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
Sea Surface Salinity (monthly)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 4
3D Salinity (monthly)	Obs	MedHYMAP	Table 10
3D Salinity (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Salinity(daily)	Regional Reanalysis	Mercator	Table 25
3D Salinity(monthly)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
Mean Sea Level (weekly)	Obs	Satellite Altimetry	Table 5
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Obs	Reconstruction	Table 26
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	Mercator	Table 25
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA Ensemble	Table 27
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	Regional Model	CMCC Ensemble	Table 28
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA Ensemble	Table 27

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Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	CMCC Ensemble	Table 28
Surface Currents (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Surface Currents(daily)	Regional Reanalysis	Mercator	Table 25
Surface Currents(daily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
3D Currents (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Currents(daily)	Regional Reanalysis	Mercator	Table 25
3D Currents(monthly)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
3D Temperature (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
3D Salinity (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA Ensemble	Table 27
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	Regional Model	CMCC Ensemble	Table 28
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA Ensemble	Table 27
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	CMCC Ensemble	Table 28

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	Model		
Surface Currents (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Currents (daily)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16
3D Currents (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Currents (monthly)	Regional Model	MedCORDEX Ensemble	Table 16

6 Baltic

6.1 Atmosphere

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 1
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	E-OBS	Table 6
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	E-OBS	Table 6
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Soil Moisture (daily)	Obs	ESA-CCI	Table 2
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE

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Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17
Soil Moisture (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	EuroCordex Ensemble	Table 17

6.2 Ocean

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 3
3D Temperature (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
Sea Surface Salinity (monthly)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 4
3D Salinity (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
Mean Sea Level (weekly)	Obs	Satellite Altimetry	Table 5
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND

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Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Surface Currents (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Surface Currents(daily)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
3D Currents (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Currents(daily)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
3D Temperature (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
3D Salinity (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND
Wind Waves (subdaily)	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND
Surface Currents (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Currents (daily)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
3D Currents (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12

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3D Currents (monthly)	Regional Model	Baltic-Earth Ensemble	Table 19
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7 Macaronesian

7.1 Atmosphere

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 1
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

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	Model		
Soil Moisture (daily)	Obs	ESA-CCI	Table 2
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Soil Moisture (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12

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Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	MENA-Cordex Ensemble	Table 18
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	ESCENA	Table 32
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

7.2 Ocean

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 3
3D Temperature (monthly)	Obs	Global Hydrographic products	Table 9
3D Temperature (monthly)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Temperature (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Hindcast	ROM simulations	Table 33
Sea Surface Salinity (monthly)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 4
3D Salinity (monthly)	Obs	Global Hydrographic products	Table 9
3D Salinity (monthly)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Salinity(daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Hindcast	ROM simulations	Table 33
Mean Sea Level (weekly)	Obs	Satellite Altimetry	Table 5
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Hindcast	ROM simulations	Table 33
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA global storm surge	Table 27
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Global Model	CMEMS	Table 24
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA Ensemble	Table 27

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Surface Currents (daily)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Surface Currents(daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Surface Currents(monthly)	Regional Hindcast	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Currents (daily)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Currents(daily)	Regional Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Currents(monthly)	Regional Hindcast	ROM simulations	Table 33

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	ESCENARIOS Ensemble	Table 23
Sea Surface Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Temperature (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	ESCENARIOS Ensemble	Table 23
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Regional Model	ESCENARIOS Ensemble	Table 23
Sea Surface Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Salinity (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	ESCENARIOS Ensemble	Table 23
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Hindcast	ROM simulations	Table 33
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Regional Model	ESCENARIOS Ensemble	Table 23
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Sea Level - meteorological tides	Regional	IMEDEA Ensemble	Table 27

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(subdaily)	Model		
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Global Model	COWCLIP Ensemble	Table 14
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA Ensemble	Table 27
Surface Currents (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Currents (daily)	Regional Model	ESCENARIOS Ensemble	Table 23
Surface Currents(monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Currents (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Currents (monthly)	Regional Model	ESCENARIOS Ensemble	Table 23
3D Currents(monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

8 Caribbean

8.1 Atmosphere

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 1
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Precipitation (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
Precipitation (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

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10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
10-m winds (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
10-m winds (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
10-m winds (daily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
10-m winds (daily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Relative humidity (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
Relative humidity (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Soil Moisture (daily)	Obs	ESA-CCI	Table 2
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Global Reanalysis	ERA-Interim	Table 11
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Precipitation (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Precipitation (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
Precipitation (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
Precipitation (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

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Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
Surface Temperature (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
10-m winds (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
10-m winds (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
10-m winds (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
10-m winds (subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Relative humidity (subdaily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Relative humidity (daily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 21
Relative humidity (daily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Relative humidity(subdaily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 20
Relative humidity(subdaily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Soil Moisture (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Soil Moisture (daily)	Regional Model	C3AF Ensemble	Table 21
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	Central America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 22
Soil Moisture (subdaily)	Regional Model	North America-Cordex Ensemble	Table 20
Soil Moisture (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

8.2 Ocean

DATA SOURCES FOR PRESENT CLIMATE			
Variable	Type	Name	Details
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 3
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional	ROM simulations	Table 33

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	Model		
3D Temperature (monthly)	Obs	Global Hydrographic products	Table 9
3D Temperature (monthly)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Sea Surface Salinity (monthly)	Obs	Satellite Observations	Table 4
Sea Surface Salinity (monthly)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
Sea Surface Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Salinity (monthly)	Obs	Global Hydrographic products	Table 9
3D Salinity (monthly)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 24
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Mean Sea Level (weekly)	Obs	Satellite Altimetry	Table 5
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 33
Mean Sea Level (daily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 24
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	Regional Model	IMEDEA global storm surge	Table 13
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Global Model	CMEMS	Table 24
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	WWIII	Table 31
Surface Currents (daily)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 33
Surface Currents (daily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 24
3D Currents (daily)	Global Reanalysis	CMEMS	Table 33
3D Currents(monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 24

DATA SOURCES FOR FUTURE CLIMATE

Variable	Type	Name	Details
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Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Temperature (daily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Temperature (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Temperature (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Surface Salinity (daily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Salinity (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Salinity (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
Mean Sea Level (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Sea Level - meteorological tides (subdaily)	Regional Model	NOT FOUND	NOT FOUND
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Global Model	COWCLIP Ensemble	Table 14
Wind Waves (subdaily)	Regional Model	WWIII	Table 31
Surface Currents (daily)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
Surface Currents (daily)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33
3D Currents (monthly)	Global Model	CMIP5 Ensemble	Table 12
3D Currents (monthly)	Regional Model	ROM simulations	Table 33

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9 Climate Change Impact Indicators (CCIIs)

In the impact chains defined in deliverable D3.2 different elements of hazard, exposure and vulnerability have been identified. Then, in D3.3 different indicators have been proposed to quantify those elements. In a later stage, the sector modelling teams (SMTs), based on that work and on the expert knowledge of the SMT participants, have selected which indicators will be used for the operationalization of the impact chains. That list of indicators has been compiled and included in this section.

A clarification is required at this point. Some of those indicators had already been computed in some regions in the past (e.g. heat waves indicators are found in the literature), but we haven't found any study in which those indicators were computed in all islands in a consistent manner. The exact definition of the indicators, the databases used for their computation and their spatiotemporal extent were not the same, so they can not be merged and/or used by the SMTs. Therefore, for the goals of the project it makes no sense to compile those indicators, specially if they are going to be recomputed in a consistent manner by WP4 and reported in D4.3.

The list of hazard indicators identified by the SMTs is presented here by sector.

9.1 Maritime Transport Sector

For the Maritime Transport Sector three hazard indicators are required and have to be calculated for both coast and open sea.

1. Annual Mean Sea Level
2. Frequency of extreme marine storm (number of days per year with Significant Wave Height maximum above the 98th percentile of a reference baseline period)
3. Frequency of extreme high winds (number of days per year with Wind speed maximum above the 98th percentile of a reference baseline period)

9.2 Aquaculture Sector

For the aquaculture sector the following indicators will consist in threshold values based on information provided by stakeholders, in particular farmers, and will be defined per species and per island. In cases where the latter information cannot be gathered, WP4 will anyway provide statistical information on the distribution of the relevant variables (e.g. return period of extreme waves, empirical frequency of values exceeding fixed percentiles, etc.).

1. Sea temperature down to 10 m
2. Wave height

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3. Currents down to 10 m

9.3 Tourism Sector

For the tourism sector the list of indicators that have been selected and requested at island level are the following:

1. Water transparency and reduction of biodiversity (linked to key species, like seagrasses which host the marine diversity).
2. Fire weather index.
3. Change in flag species in the Balearic Islands. It is not clear yet if we can produce this for other islands as a deep knowledge of the species characteristic is needed.
4. % of beach reduction (where local data is available), related to coastal inundation
5. A single indicator for thermal confort or optimal days
6. The length of the window of opportunity for vectors to be introduced (emergent diseases).
7. % of water available from natural sources (precipitation minus evapotranspiration)
8. Coastal storms indices at yearly scale and for summer periods (damage to infrastructures)

9.4 Energy Sector

For the energy sector the selected indicators are the following:

1. Change in photovoltaic productivity (kWh/kW)
2. Change in wind energy productivity (kWh/kW)
3. Periods of low wind energy productivity (thresholds + duration)
4. Periods of low solar energy productivity (thresholds + duration)
5. Periods of combined low solar and wind energy productivity (thresholds + duration)
6. Extreme wind measure (98th percentile)
7. extreme temperature (98th percentile)
8. Indicator of Flood occurrence
9. Extreme temperatures
10. Coastal waves
11. Storm surges, coastal erosion (only test cases, much data needed)
12. Cooling degree days (°C)
13. Standardised precipitation index

Nr	Hazard Indicator	Variables required to compute the indicator
MT-1	Annual Mean Sea Level	Mean Sea level fields
MT-2	Frequency of extreme marine storm	Mean Sea level fields Storm surges Wave fields
MT-3	Frequency of extreme high winds	Wind fields
A-1	Sea temperature down to 10 m	Ocean Temperature
A-2	Frequency of extreme wave height events according to fixed thresholds (to be determined)	Wave fields
A-3	Currents down to 10 m	Ocean currents
T-1	Water transparency and reduction of biodiversity using the reduction of seagrass extension	Ocean Temperature until 100 m
T-2	Fire weather index	Temperature Humidity Wind Precipitation
T-3	% of change in flag species in the Balearic Islands	To be defined
T-4	% of beach reduction	Mean Sea Level Storm surge Waves Detailed bathy-topography
T-5	Change in the number of optimal days for beach activities	Temperature Cloud cover Precipitation Wind intensity

		Relative humidity
T-6	The length of the window of opportunity for vectors to be introduced (emergent diseases).	To be defined
T-7	% of change of water available from natural sources	Precipitation Evapotranspiration Runoff
T-8	Coastal storms indices at yearly scale and for summer periods	Storm surges Wind fields Mean Sea Level
E-1	Change in photovoltaic productivity	Surface solar Radiation, Temperature
E-2	Change in wind energy productivity	Wind speed at different levels 10-100 m
E-3	Periods of low wind energy productivity	Wind speed at different levels 10-100 m
E-4	Periods of low solar energy productivity	Surface solar Radiation Temperature
E-5	Periods of combined low solar and wind energy productivity	Wind speed at different levels 10-100 m Surface solar Radiation, Temperature
E-6	Extreme wind intensity	Wind
E-7	Extreme temperature	Temperature
E-8	Probability of flood occurrence	Sea Level Waves
E-9	Extreme temperatures	Temperature

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E-10	Extreme coastal waves	Wave fields
E-11	Storm surges	Storm surges
E-12	Cooling degree days	Temperature
E-13	Standardised precipitation index/available water	Precipitation

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10 TABLES

Table 1 Precipitation Observations from Satellite data

Variable
Precipitation
Domain
Global
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Several sources
Period :
Historical. Time coverage variable, depending on the satellite SSMI: 1987 - present TMI: 1997- present
Data Availability:
Registration required at http://mistrals.sedoo.fr/?editDatsId=617&datsId=617&project_name=HyMeX Alternatively, NASA website may provide also precipitation data from satellite observations.
Data Storage
In the Web

Table 2 Soil Moisture Observations from Satellite data

Variable
Soil Moisture
Domain
Global
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Several sources
Period :
Historical. Daily data for 1978-2010 (at least) 0.25° Spatial resolution Recommended to use the merged active and passive products
Data Availability:
Registration required at https://www.esa-soilmoisture-cci.org/node/139 More information on the product at https://www.esa-soilmoisture-cci.org/sites/default/files/documents/M6/ESA_CCI_SM_PSD_D1.2.1_version_4.2.pdf
Data Storage

In the Web

Table 3: Sea Surface Temperature Observations from Satellite data

Variable
Sea Surface Temperature
Domain
Global
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Copernicus Marine Service
Period :
Covering the global ocean from 1987 to present at different spatial resolutions Daily and monthly products
Data Availability:
Registration required at http://marine.copernicus.eu/
Alternatively, NASA website may provide also SST products from satellite
Data Storage
In the Web

Table 4: Sea Surface Salinity Observations from Satellite data

Variable
Sea Surface Salinity from SMOS
Domain
Global Ocean, North Atlantic and Mediterranean
Source
Barcelona Expert Center
Period :
2010-2016, monthly fields Advanced products for global ocean, Mediterranean and North Atlantic
Data Availability:
Freely Available at http://bec.icm.csic.es/
Data Storage
In the web
More information
Olmedo et al., 2016] Olmedo, E., Martínez, J., Umbert, M., Hoareau, N., Portabella, M., Ballabrera, J., Turiel, A. (2016). Improving time and space resolution of SMOS salinity maps using multifractal fusion. Remote Sensing of Environment 180, 246-263. DOI:

Table 5: Sea Level Observations from Satellite data

Variable
Sea Level
Domain
Global and Mediterranean
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Copernicus Marine Service
Period :
Covering the global ocean from 1993 to present at 1/4° and covering the Mediterranean at 1/8°. Daily and monthly products, although the actual satellite revisiting time at each location is ~7 days.
Data Availability:
Registration required at http://marine.copernicus.eu/
Data Storage
In the Web

Table 6:E-OBS gridded dataset

Variable
Daily mean temperature TG , daily minimum temperature TN , daily maximum temperature TX , daily precipitation sum RR and daily averaged sea level pressure PP
Domain
Europe
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
E-OBS
Period :
They cover the area: 25N-75N x 40W-75E. The data files are in compressed NetCDF format and range in size from 88Mb - 1.2Gb. There are 4 different versions: 2 grid resolutions x 2 grid flavours. Data is made available on a 0.25 and 0.5 degree regular lat-lon grid, as well as on a 0.22 and 0.44 degree rotated pole grid, with the north pole at 39.25N, 162W
Data Availability:
Registration required at https://www.ecad.eu/download/ensembles/download.php
Data Storage

In the Web

Table 7: Safran - France gridded dataset

Variable
Precipitation, temperature, humidity, winds, surface pressure
Domain
France
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Safran
Period : 1958-2014
Data Availability:
Registration required at http://mistrals.sedoo.fr/?editDatsId=47&datsId=47&project_name=HyMeX&q=safra
Data Storage
In the Web
Additional Information
Quintana Seguí, P.; Le Moigne, P.; Durand, Y.; Martin, E.; Habets, F.; Baillon, M.; Canellas, C.; Franchisteguy, L. & Morel, S. Analysis of Near-Surface Atmospheric Variables: Validation of the SAFRAN Analysis over France Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology, 2008, 47, 92-107 Vidal, J.-P.; Martin, E.; Franchistéguy, L.; Baillon, M. & Soubeyroux, J.-M. A 50-year high-resolution atmospheric reanalysis over France with the Safran system International Journal of Climatology, 2010, 30, 1627-1644

Table 8: Safran - Spain gridded dataset

Variable
Precipitation, temperature, humidity, winds, surface pressure
Domain
Spain
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Safran
Period : 1958-2014
Data Availability:
Registration required at http://mistrals.sedoo.fr/?editDatsId=1388&datsId=1388&project_name=HyMeX&q=safra
Data Storage
In the Web

Additional Information
Quintana-Seguí, P., Peral, M. C., Turco, M., Llasat, M.-C., & Martin, E. (2016). Meteorological analysis systems in north-east Spain. Validation of SAFRAN and SPAN. Journal of Environmental Informatics, In Press. http://doi.org/10.3808/jei.201600335 Validation of a new SAFRAN-based gridded precipitation product for Spain and comparisons to Spain02 and ERA-Interim, Quintana-Seguí, P., Turco, M., Herrera, S., & Miguez-Macho, G., Hydrology and Earth System Sciences 21(4), 2187–2201. DOI: 10.5194/HESS-21-2187-2017.

Table 9: Global Ocean hydrographic product

Variable
3D monthly Temperature and Salinity
Domain
Global
Source
EN4
Period :
Covering the global ocean from 1900 to 2017 at 1° of spatial resolution
Data Availability:
Freely available at https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/en4/download-en4-2-0.html
Data Storage
In the Web
More information
Good, S. A., M. J. Martin and N. A. Rayner, 2013. EN4: quality controlled ocean temperature and salinity profiles and monthly objective analyses with uncertainty estimates, Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans, 118, 6704-6716, doi:10.1002/2013JC009067

Table 10: MedHYMAP hydrographic gridded dataset

Variable
3D monthly Temperature and Salinity
Domain
Mediterranean
Source
MedHYMAP
Period :
Covering the Mediterranean from 1950 to 2016 with 1/8° spatial resolution. Monthly fields. Based on optimal interpolation of historical temperature and salinity profiles.

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Data Availability:
Under Request at gabriel.jorda@ieo.es
Data Storage
Downloaded

Table 11: Era-Interim global Reanalysis

Variable
All atmospheric variables
Domain
Global
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
ERA-Interim ECMWF
Period :
1979-Present
Data Availability:
Registration required at http://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/interim-full-daily/levtype=sfc/
Other global reanalyses are available but performance is not clearly better than for ERA-i If needed check reanalyses.org for a complete overview.
Data Storage
In the Web
Additional Information
Dee DP, Uppala SM, Simmons AJ, Berrisford P, Poli P, Kobayashi S, Andrae U, Balmaseda MA, Balsamo G, Bauer P, Bechtold P, Beljaars ACM, van de Berg L, Bidlot J, Bormann N, Delsol C, Dragani R, Fuentes M, Geer AJ, Haimberger L, Healy SB, Hersbach H, Holm EV, Isaksen L, Kallberg P, Kohler M, Matricardi M, McNally AP, Monge-Sanz BM, Morcrette J-J, Park B-K, Peubey C, de Rosnay P, Tavolato C, Thepaut J-N, Vitart F. 2011. The ERA-Interim reanalysis: configuration and performance of the data assimilation system. Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc. 137: 553–597. DOI:10.1002/qj.828

Table 12: CMIP5 Ensemble of Atmosphere Global Climate Models

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
All atmospheric and oceanographic fields
Domain covered by the dataset
Global
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Couple Multimodel Intercomparison Project - Phase 5

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Period : <i>Evaluation, Control, Scenario</i> (
More than 30 institutions with their own model provide historical, pre-industrial control and RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5 (among others) scenario data.
Details of the CMIP5 https://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/pdf/10.1175/BAMS-D-11-00094.1
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
Public database after registration. See instructions in https://cmip.llnl.gov/cmip5/availability.html
Several nodes are available to download the data
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)
Partially downloaded, partially in the web

Table 13:IMEDEA global storm surge simulation

Variable
Sea Level - storm surge
Domain
Global
Source
Period :
Covering the global ocean from 1850 to 2015 at variable spatial resolution. Using a finite element grid with high resolution close to the coast.
Data Availability:
Under request to gabriel.jorda@ieo.es
Data Storage
Downloaded

Table 14:COWCLIP wind wave global projections

Variable
Wind Wave parameters
Domain
Global
Source
COWCLIP project
Period :
Covering the global ocean at 1° of spatial resolution. Historical , and projections (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) forced by GCMs: MRI-CGCM3 MIROC5

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<p>INMCM4 HadGEM2-ES GFDL-CM3 CNRM-CM5 BCC-CSM1.1 ACCESS1.0</p> <p>Outputs are delivered for Mid XXI century and End of XXI century</p>
<p>Data Availability: Freely available at http://tds.csiro.au/thredds/catalog/Global_wave_projections/catalog.html</p>
<p>Data Storage In the web</p>
<p>For more information http://www.nature.com/nclimate/journal/vaop/ncurrent/full/nclimate1791.html</p>

Table 15: MedCORDEX Ensemble of Atmosphere Regional Climate Models

<p>Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics) All atmospheric fields</p>
<p>Domain Mediterranean</p>
<p>Source (project, initiative, etc...) Med-CORDEX (www.medcordex.eu)</p>
<p>Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i>(specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)</p>
<p>Historical, Control and Scenario with atmosphere stand-alone models:</p> <p>Number of participating institutes: 14 Number of participating different RCMs: 9 Number of evaluation runs completed: 27 (including 5 runs at 20-30 km and 6 runs at 10-12km) Number of historical runs completed: 15 runs (including 4 runs at 12-25km) Number of RCP8.5 runs completed: 14 runs (including 4 runs at 12-25km) Number of RCP4.5 runs completed: 6 runs (including 2 runs at 12km) Number of RCP2.6 runs completed: 2 runs (including 1 run at 12km) Number of runs planned in total: 77 Number of runs completed: 64 Number of runs in the database: 45</p> <p>Details of the atmosphere stand-alone runs: https://www.medcordex.eu/Tabelle_RUNs/Listofruns_Med-CORDEX_phase1_ARCM.pdf</p>

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<p>Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models: Number of evaluation runs completed: 12 (including 5 runs with the river coupling) Number of historical runs completed: 7 runs (including 4 runs with the river coupling) Number of RCP8.5 runs completed: 6 runs (including 3 runs with the river coupling) Number of RCP4.5 runs completed: 4 runs (including 1 run with the river coupling) Number of RCP2.6 runs completed: 1 run (including 1 run with the river coupling) Number of runs planned in total: 36 Number of runs completed: 30 Number of runs in the database: 14</p> <p>Details of the coupled ocean-atmosphere runs https://www.medcordex.eu/Tabelle_RUNs/Listofruns_Med-CORDEX_phase1_RCSM.pdf</p>
<p>Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)</p>
<p>Public database access after registration https://www.medcordex.eu/</p> <p>If some fields are not in the database they could be requested to the data producer</p> <p>CMCC simulations ((http://www.cmcc.it/) can be accessed under request to enrico.scoccimarro@cmcc.it</p>
<p>Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)</p>
<p>In the web</p>

Table 16: MedCORDEX Ensemble of Ocean Regional Climate Models

<p>Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)</p>
<p>All atmospheric fields</p>
<p>Domain</p>
<p>Mediterranean</p>
<p>Source (project, initiative, etc...)</p>
<p>Med-CORDEX (www.medcordex.eu)</p>
<p>Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i>(specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)</p>
<p>Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models: Number of evaluation runs completed: 12 (including 5 runs with the river coupling) Number of historical runs completed: 7 runs (including 4 runs with the river coupling) Number of RCP8.5 runs completed: 6 runs (including 3 runs with the river coupling) Number of RCP4.5 runs completed: 4 runs (including 1 run with the river coupling) Number of RCP2.6 runs completed: 1 run (including 1 run with the river coupling) Number of runs planned in total: 36 Number of runs completed: 30 Number of runs in the database: 14</p>

<p>Details of the coupled ocean-atmosphere runs https://www.medcordex.eu/Tabelle_RUNs/Listofruns_Med-CORDEX_phase1_RCSM.pdf</p>
<p>Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)</p> <p>Public database access after registration https://www.medcordex.eu/</p> <p>If some fields are not in the database they could be requested to the data producer</p> <p>CMCC simulations (http://www.cmcc.it/) can be accessed under request to enrico.scoccimarro@cmcc.it</p>
<p>Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)</p> <p>In the web</p>

Table 17: EuroCORDEX Ensemble of Atmosphere Regional Climate Models

<p>Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)</p> <p>All atmospheric fields</p>
<p>Domain</p> <p>European-Mediterranean</p>
<p>Source (project, initiative, etc...)</p> <p>EURO-CORDEX (https://euro-cordex.net/)</p>
<p>Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i>(specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)</p>
<p>Historical, Control and Scenario with atmosphere stand-alone models:</p> <p>Number of participating institutes: 30 Number of participating different RCMs: 12 Number of evaluation runs completed: 46 runs (17 at 12.5 km resolution, 29 at 50 km resolution) Number of historical runs completed: 97runs (43 at 12.5 km, 54 at 50 km) Number of RCP8.5 runs completed: 73 runs (37 at 12.5 km, 36 at 50 km) Number of RCP4.5 runs completed: 58 runs (25 at 12.5 km, 33 at 50 km) Number of RCP2.6 runs completed: 37 runs (18 at 12.5 km, 19 at 50 km) Number of runs planned in total: 339 Number of runs completed: 311 Number of runs in the database: 175</p> <p>Details of the atmosphere stand-alone runs: https://euro-cordex.net/imperia/md/content/csc/cordex/20180130-eurocordex-simulations.pdf</p>
<p>Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models:</p>

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No coupled model simulations
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
Public database access after registration: Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) nodes listed at https://euro-cordex.net/060378/index.php.en
If some fields are not in the database they could be requested to the data producer
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)
In the web

Table 18: MENA-CORDEX Ensemble of Atmosphere Regional Climate Models

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
All atmospheric fields
Domain covered by the dataset
Middle East North Africa
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
MENA-CORDEX
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)
Number of participating institutes: 7 Number of participating different RCMs: 7 Number of evaluation runs completed: 8 (6 for 50-km, 2 for 25-km) Number of historical runs completed: 13 runs (10 for 50-km, 3 for 25-km) Number of RCP8.5 runs completed: 11 runs (9 for 50-km, 2 for 25-km) Number of RCP4.5 runs completed: 11 runs (10 for 50-km, 1 for 25-km) Number of RCP2.6 runs completed: 2 runs (for 50-km) Number of runs planned in total: 45 (including Evaluation, Historical and Scenario) Number of runs completed: 45 Number of runs in the database: 16
Details of the MENA-CORDEX initiative: http://mena-cordex.cyi.ac.cy/
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
Public database after registration: https://esg-dn1.nsc.liu.se/projects/esgf-liu/ or for simulations not uploaded in the CORDEX ESGF data portal contact the contributors (http://mena-cordex.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/contributors) or g.zittis@cyi.ac.cy
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)
Partially downloaded, partially in the web

Table 19: Baltic Earth Ensemble of Ocean Regional Climate Models

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Variable
All ocean variables (Temperature, Salinity, Currents, Mean Sea Level)
Domain
Mediterranean Region
Source
Baltic Earth
Period :
The ocean model has a resolution of 2 nautical miles ($dx=1/18*\cos(\phi)$ degree, $dy=1/30$ degree) and 56 levels in the vertical with a resolution of 3 m at the surface increasing to 9 m at 100 m depth to a maximum of 22 m at 700 m in the Norwegian Trench.
There is the group at the DMI who is running or has run scenarios with uncoupled HBM and coupled Hirlam-HBM (Tian Tain at dmi dk)
The MPI in Hamburg has run and is running coupled scenarios with their global ocean, regional atmosphere model (Uwe Mikolajewicz).
The Institute of Marine Research at the University Hamburg (Thomas Pohlmann) has used their system REMO-HAMSOM to run scenarios for the North Sea. The Baltic Sea is not included here.
There is also a SRES A1B scenario by Dmitry Sein (now at AWI) with the REMO-MPIOM model where MPIOM has a grid focussed on northern Germany (North Pole).
The IOW in Warnemünde is building a coupled system for the Baltic Sea.
The HZG in Geesthacht together with the DWD is also working on a coupled system for the Northern Europe including the Baltic Sea (Joanna Staneva, Jennifer Brauch, Ha Hagemann).
Data Availability:
Under Request to each group
Data Storage
Downloaded

Table 20:C3AF Atmospheric climate simulations

Variable
All atmospheric fields Precipitation - 6h Surface temperature - 6h 10m wind - 6h
Domain
Global grid stretched with a focus with 10-15km resolution on the east side of lesser Antilles arc. Subgridded <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 km over the cyclonic basin • 50 km North Atlantic

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Source (project, initiative, etc...)
European Project C3AF (Climate Change and Consequences in the French West Indies)
Period :
Historical, Control and Scenario with atmosphere stand-alone models: Historical: 1965 – 2014 Future period: 2020 – 2080 Scenario: RCP 8.5 2020 2080 Spatial resolution: 10-15 km Two runs of monthly SST 1965 – 2014 (ARPEGE H + ARPEGE H mSST) Climatic model Météo-France: ARPEGE F (Centered on the tropical North Atlantic)
Data Availability:
Public database access after the end of the project (December 2019) If some fields are not in the database they could be requested to the data producers. Contact: philippe.palany@meteo.fr
Data Storage
METEOFRACTANCE Toulouse and METEOFRACTANCE Martinique
More Information
ARPEGE-Climate Version 6.2. Algorithmic Documentation. MF CNRM. Jan 2017 Voltaire, A. et al., 2013. The CNRM-CM5.1 global climate model: description and basic evaluation. <i>Climate Dynamics</i> , 40(9–10), pp.2091–2121. Available at: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00382-011-1259-y . Batté, L. & Déqué, M., 2016. Randomly correcting model errors in the ARPEGE-Climate v6.1 component of CNRM-CM: applications for seasonal forecasts. <i>Geoscientific Model Development</i> , 9(6), pp.2055–2076. Available at: https://www.geosci-model-dev.net/9/2055/2016/ .

Table 21:Central America - CORDEX

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
All atmospheric fields
Domain covered by the dataset
Latin America and the Caribbean
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
The LAC CORDEX program
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)
these simulations run from 1950-2100 with a spatial resolution of 0.44°/50km. Number of participating institutes: 5 Number of participating different RCMs: 3 Number of evaluation runs completed: 3

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Number of historical runs completed: 8 Number of RCP8.5 runs completed: 5 Number of RCP4.5 runs completed: 4
http://www.cordex-lac.org/model-simulations
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
Public database after registration https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/esgf-llnl/
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)
In the web
More information
Details in http://www.cordex-lac.org

Table 22:North America - CORDEX

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
All atmospheric fields
Domain covered by the dataset
North America
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
The North American CORDEX program
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)
These simulations run from 1950-2100 with a spatial resolution of 0.22°/25km or 0.44°/50km.
Number of participating institutes: 7 Number of participating different RCMs: 7 Number of evaluation runs completed: 9 (7 for 50-km, 2 for 4-km) Number of historical runs completed: 26 runs (13 for 50-km, 13 for 25-km) Number of RCP8.5 runs completed: 27 runs (13 for 50-km, 14 for 25-km) Number of RCP4.5 runs completed: 7 runs (6 for 50-km, 1 for 25-km) Number of RCP2.6 runs completed: 1 runs (for 50-km)
https://na-cordex.org/simulation-matrix
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
Public database after registration https://na-cordex.org/data-access
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)
In the web
More information
Details of the NA-CORDEX initiative:

<https://na-cordex.org/>

Mearns, L.O., et al., 2017: *The NA-CORDEX dataset*, version 1.0. NCAR Climate Data Gateway, Boulder CO, accessed [date], <https://doi.org/10.5065/D6SJ1JCH>

Table 23: ESCENARIOS ocean regional climate ensemble

Variable		
Ocean Variables (currents, temperature, salinity, mean sea level)		
Domain		
NE Atlantic		
Source (project, initiative, etc...)		
VANIMEDAT-2, ESCENARIOS		
Period :		
Historical (1958-2001/1958-2010), Control +scenario (1950-2100) for B2, A1B and A2		
Historical, Control and Scenario with atmospheric forcing from various sources:		
Simulations produced with NEMO at 1/12° Spatial resolution		
Forcing provided by		
Hindcast	1960- 2000	1 h. Downscaling of ERA-40
Hindcast	1989- 2004	1 h. Downscaling of ERA-Interim
Control	1961-2000	1 h. Downscaling of ECHAM5
Control	1961-2000	1 h. Downscaling of HadCM3- low
Projection A1B	2001-2050	1 h. Downscaling of ECHAM5
Projection A1B	2001-2050	1 h. Downscaling of HadCM3- low
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)		
Under request to gabriel.jorda@ieo.es		
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)		
Downloaded		
More Information		
Gomis D., Álvarez-Fanjul E., Jordà G., Marcos M., Aznar R., Rodríguez-Camino E., Sánchez-Perrino J.C., Rodríguez-González J.M., Martínez-Asensio A., Llasses J., Pérez B., Sotillo M.G. 2016. Regional marine climate scenarios in the NE Atlantic sector close to the Spanish shores. <i>Sci. Mar.</i> 80S1: 215-234. doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.3989/scimar.04328.07A		

Table 24: Copernicus Marine Service - Regional Reanalysis

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Variable
All ocean variables (Temperature, Salinity, Currents, Mean Sea Level and Wind waves)
Domain
Global, Iberian-Biscay-Ireland Region, Mediterranean Region and Baltic Region
Source
Copernicus Marine Service
Period :
Covering different domains at different spatial resolutions: Global product ~ 25km. Regional products ~3-6 km Daily and monthly fields.
Data Availability:
Registration required at http://marine.copernicus.eu/
Data Storage
In the Web

Table 25:Mercator Ocean - Regional Reanalysis

Variable
All ocean variables (Temperature, Salinity, Currents, Mean Sea Level)
Domain
Mediterranean Region
Source
Copernicus Marine Service
Period :
Covering the global ocean from 1987 to present at different spatial resolutions Daily and monthly products
Data Availability:
Under Request to Jonathan Beuvier jbeuvier@mercator-ocean.fr
Data Storage
Downloaded

Table 26:Mediterranean Sea Level Reconstruction based on a combination of tide gauge data and spatial covariances from satellite altimetry.

Variable
Mediterranean sea level reconstruction
Domain
Mediterranean

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Source
Period : Covering the Mediterranean from 1950 to 2008 with 1/8° spatial resolution. Monthly fields.
Data Availability: Under Request at gabriel.jorda@ieo.es
Data Storage Downloaded
More information 10.1016/j.gloplacha.2011.09.003

Table 27: IMEDEA Ensemble of storm surge and wind wave simulations

Variable		
Wave parameters: SWH, Mean frequency, mean direction Sea Level : Sea level height, variability only forced by atmospheric pressure and winds.		
Domain		
Mediterranean Sea and North Atlantic		
Source (project, initiative, etc...)		
VANIMEDAT-2, ESCENARIOS		
Period :		
Historical (1958-2001/1958-2010), Control +scenario (1950-2100) for B2, A1B and A2		
Historical, Control and Scenario with RCM wind fields of various sources: All wave simulation produced with the WAM model (1/8°, only Western Med). Sea Level simulation produced with HAMSOM model (1/6°, whole Med and NE Atlantic)		
Forcing provided by		
Hindcast	1958-2001	1h. Downscaling of ERA40
Hindcast	1989-2008	1h. Downscaling of ERA-Interim
Control	1950-2000	1h. Downscaling of ECHAM5
Control	1950-2000	1h. Downscaling of HadCM3-low
Control	1950-2000	1h. Downscaling of HadCM3-ref
Control	1950-2000	1h. Downscaling of HadCM3-high
Control	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of CNRM (Just Med)
Projection A1B	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of ECHAM5
Projection A1B	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of HadCM3-low
Projection A1B	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of HadCM3-ref
Projection A1B	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of HadCM3-high

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Projection B2	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of CNRM (Just Med)
Projection A1B	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of CNRM (Just Med)
Projection A2	2001-2100	1h. Downscaling of CNRM (Just Med)
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)		
Under request to gabriel.jorda@ieo.es		
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)		
Downloaded		
More Information		
Gomis D., Álvarez-Fanjul E., Jordà G., Marcos M., Aznar R., Rodríguez-Camino E., Sánchez-Perrino J.C., Rodríguez-González J.M., Martínez-Asensio A., Llasses J., Pérez B., Sotillo M.G. 2016. Regional marine climate scenarios in the NE Atlantic sector close to the Spanish shores. Sci. Mar. 80S1: 215-234. doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.3989/scimar.04328.07A		
Jordà G., Gomis D., Álvarez-Fanjul E., et al. 2012. Atmospheric contribution to Mediterranean and nearby Atlantic sea level variability under different climate change scenarios. Global Planet. Change, 80-81: 198-214. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha .		

Table 28: CMCC Ensemble of storm surge and wind wave simulations

Variable
Wave parameters: SWH, Mean frequency, mean direction Sea Level : Sea level height, variability only forced by atmospheric pressure and winds.
Domain
Mediterranean Sea
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
CIRCE EUfp6 and RISES-AMEUfp7
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i>
Historical+scenario (1950-2100) for RCP4.5 and 8.5 Historical+scenario (1950-2050) for A1B
Historical, Control and Scenario with RCM wind fields of various sources: All wave simulation produced with the WAM model (1/4° spatial resolution). Sea Level produced with the HYPSE model (1/5° spatial resolution)
Forcing provided by "Circe" projections (1951-2050)
CMCC LR A1B 1951-2050
CMCC HR A1B 1970-2050
MPI A1B 1951-2050
ENEA A1B 1951-2050
ARPEGE A1B 1951-2050
IPSL3 A1B 1951-2050

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IPSL2	A1B 1951-2050
CMIP5 driven "MedCORDEX" projections (1951-2100)	
CMCC	historical rcp4.5 rcp8.5
ITU	historical rcp8.5
LMD	historical rcp4.5 rcp8.5
CNRM	historical rcp4.5 rcp8.5
GUF	historical rcp4.5 rcp8.5
RCA4	historical rcp8.5
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)	
We are working on this	
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)	
TBD	
More Information	
Lionello P, Conte D, Marzo L, Scarascia L (2016) The contrasting effect of increasing mean sea level and decreasing storminess on the maximum water level during storms along the coast of the Mediterranean Sea in the mid 21st century. <i>Glob Planet Change</i> http://dxdoiorg/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2016.06.012	

Table 29: Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan for Madeira Region - Atmospheric regional climate dynamical downscaling Model from GRM HadCM3

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
Mean Temperature, Max. Temperature, Min. Temperature, accumulated precipitation and relative humidity (Max. and Min.)
Domain
Madeira
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan for Madeira Region
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)
The information was produced by year and considering 4 temporal periods: 1970-1990; 2010-2039; 2040-2069 and 2070-2099, and 2 SRES scenarios A2 and B2.
Historical, Control and Scenario with atmosphere stand-alone models: Dynamic Regionalization based on Global Model HadCM3.
Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models: <u>No coupled model simulations</u>

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<p>Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)</p> <p>Database access: link in http://clima-madeira.pt/pt/cartografia/#?mapindex=0&lat=32.7500&lng=-16.9600&zoom=11</p> <p>The statistical downscaling methodologies based on AGCM and RCM Simulations. If some fields are not in the database they could be requested to the data producers. Contact: Henrique Rodrigues - eduardo.mv.azevedo@uac.pt</p>
<p>Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)</p> <p>In the web or Local government web platform: Contact: Henrique Rodrigues-henriquerodrigues@gov-madeira.pt</p>
<p>More Information</p> <p>Miranda, P.M.A., M.A.Valente, A.R. Tomé, R. Trigo, F. Coelho, A. Aguiar & E.B. Azevedo.2006. O clima de Portugal nos séculos XX e XXI. 2º Capítulo in Santos, F.D. e P. Miranda (Editores): Alterações climáticas em Portugal: Cenários, impactos e medidas de adaptação - Projecto SIAM II. Gradiva, Lisboa, Portugal, 506pp.</p> <p>Miranda, S. 2003. Clima da Madeira, Estágio de Licenciatura em Ciências Geofísicas, Fac. Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa.</p> <p>Osborn, T.J., K.R. Briffa, S.F.B. Tett, P.D. Jones & R.M. Trigo. 1999. Evaluation of the North Atlantic Oscillation as simulated by a coupled climate model. <i>Climate Dynamics</i> 15:685- 702.</p> <p>Santos, F.D. & P. Miranda (Editores). 2006. Alterações climáticas em Portugal: Cenários, impactos e medidas de adaptação - Projecto SIAM II. Gradiva, Lisboa, Portugal, 506pp.</p> <p>Tomé, A.R. & P.M.A. Miranda. 2004. Piecewise linear fitting and trend changing points of climate parameters, <i>Geophysical Research Letters</i> 31:L02207, doi:12.1029/2003G019100.</p> <p>Tomé, A.R. & P.M.A. Miranda. 2005. Continuous partial trends and low-frequency oscillations of time series. <i>Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics</i>, 12:451-460.</p> <p>Trigo, R.M., T.J. Osborn & J. Corte-Real. 2002. The North Atlantic Oscillation influence on Europe: climate impacts and associated physical mechanisms. <i>Climate Research</i> 20:9-17.</p> <p>Walpe, A.M. & J.H. Lawrimore (Editores). 2003. State of the Climate in 2002. <i>Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society</i> 84:Nº6, S1-S68</p>

Table 30: Regional Program for Climate Change Project - Atmospheric regional climate dynamical downscaling Model – CIELO

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Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
Mean Temperature, Max. Temperature, Min. Temperature, accumulated precipitation and relative humidity (Max. and Min.)
Domain
Azores
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Regional Program for Climate Change
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution)
<p>The information was produced monthly and aggregated for 30 years periods considering 4 temporal timings: 1960-1990; 2010-2039; 2040-2069 e 2070-2099, and 2 RCPs: RCP 4.5 and 8.5). Additionally, anomalies were calculated and 84 different themes in GIS format are available.</p> <p>Historical/Control: 1960-1990; Spatial resolution: 100 m</p> <p>Runs Scenario for 2010-2039; 2040-2069 and 2070-2099 for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 Spatial resolution: 100 m (not available)</p>
<p>Historical, Control and Scenario with atmosphere stand-alone models: The dynamical downscaling methodologies based on AGCM and RCM simulations</p> <p>Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models: <u>No coupled model simulations</u></p>
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
<p>Database access: link in http://prac.fc.ul.pt</p> <p>The dynamical downscaling methodologies based on AGCM and RCM Simulations. If some fields are not in the database they could be requested to the data producers. Contact: Eduardo Brito de Azevedo - eduardo.mv.azevedo@uac.pt</p>
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)
<p>In the web or Local government web platform:</p> <p>Contact: Ana Moreira - Ana.CP.Moreira@azores.gov.pt</p>
More Information
<p>AZEVEDO, E. B.; (1996) - Modelação do Clima Insular à Escala Local. Modelo CIELO aplicado à Ilha Terceira – Tese de Doutoramento pela Universidade dos Açores na especialidade das Ciências do Ambiente. (247p).</p> <p>AZEVEDO, E. B.; PEREIRA, L. S.; ITIER, B. (1998) – Modeling the Local Climate in Islands Envrinments. Orographic Clouds Cover – In: R.S.Schmenauer & Bridman (Eds.). First International Conference on Fog and Fog Collection. IDRC, Ottawa, Canada. Pp 433-436</p> <p>AZEVEDO, E. B.; PEREIRA, L. S.; ITIER, B. (1999a) – Simulation of local Climate in Islands Environments Using a GIS Integrated Model – Emerging Technologies for Sustainable Land Use and Water Management. – Musy et al. (Eds.), Presses Polytechniques et Universitaires Romandes. Lausanne, Switzerland.</p> <p>AZEVEDO, E. B.; PEREIRA, L. S.; ITIER, B. (1999b) – Modeling the local Climate in island environments: Water Balance Applications – Agricultural Water Management 40 (1999) 393-403.</p> <p>SANTOS, F.D.; VALENTE M.A.; MIRANDA P.M.A.; AGUIAR A., AZEVEDO, E.B.; TOMÉ A.; COELHO F.E. (2004): “CLIMATE CHANGE SCENARIOS IN THE AZORES AND MADEIRA</p>

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ISLANDS”, World Resource Review, 16, No 3, 473-491
 MIRANDA, P.M.; A., M.A. VALENTE, A.R. TOMÉ, R.TRIGO, M. F. COELHO, A. AGUIAR, E. B. AZEVEDO (2006): “O CLIMA DE PORTUGAL NOS SÉCULOS XX E XXI”, F. D. Santos e P. Miranda (editores) Alterações Climáticas em Portugal - Cenários Impactos e Medidas de Adaptação - Projeto SIAM_II, Gradiva, Lisboa, 2006.
 AZEVEDO, E.B. (2001) – “Condicionantes Dinâmicas do Clima do Arquipélago dos Açores. Elementos para o seu” – AÇOREANA. Boletim da Sociedade de Estudos Açorianos “Afonso Chaves” 9 (3): 309-317.
http://data-portal.ecmwf.int/data/d/interim_daily/

Table 31:WWIII - C3AF wave simulations – North Atlantic and French West Indies domain

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
Waves and Sea state temporal resolution: MFWAM : 3h WWIII: 1h
Domain
North Atlantic basin - MFWAM Lesser Antilles – Guadeloupe Martinique and St Marteen - St Barthelemy _ WWIII
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
METEO-FRANCE – C3AF
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution) Evaluation (1985-2014); Scenario (2051-2080) for RCP8.5 Spatial resolution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 km MFWAM • 200m WWIII
Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models: <u>Coupled model simulations with the global model CNRM-CM6 as forcing of ARPEGe climat that feed the MFWAM Atlantic that force the WWIII regional wave model</u>
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
On demand. Contact: philippe.palany@meteo.fr
More Information
Bel Madani, A., Palany P., Dalphinnet, A., Pilon, R., Chauvin, F., 2017. Future Changes in Cyclonic Wave Climate in the North Atlantic, with a Focus on the French west Indies. NH51A-0809 AGU fall meeting, New Orleans.

Table 32:ESCENA ensemble of Atmospheric Regional Climate Models

SOCLIMPACT

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
All atmospheric fields
Domain
Macaronesian
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
ESCENA (Spanish project)
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution) Evaluation (1989-2008); Control+Scenario (1950-2050) for B1, A1B and A2 Spatial resolution: 25 km
Historical, Control and Scenario with atmosphere stand-alone models: Number of participating institutes: 4 Number of participating different RCMs: 5 Number of evaluation runs completed: 5 runs Number of historical runs completed: 20 runs Number of A1B runs completed: 11 runs Number of A2 runs: 4 runs Number of B1 runs completed: 3 runs RCMs: PROMES, MM5, WRF, REMO Driving GCMs: ECHAM5 r2, HadCM3-Q3 (low sensitivity), HadCM3-Q16 (high sensitivity), ARPEGE (version 3)
Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models: <u>No coupled model simulations</u>
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
Public database access after registration: instructions and link in http://meteo.unican.es/en/projects/escena If some fields are not in the database they could be requested to the data producers. Contact: Miguel.Gaertner@uclm.es
Data Storage (Already downloaded, in the web, ...)
In the web
More Information
Jiménez-Guerrero, P., Montávez, J. P., Domínguez, M., Romera, R., Fita, L., Fernández, J., ... & Gaertner, M. A. (2013). Mean fields and interannual variability in RCM simulations over Spain: the ESCENA project. <i>Climate Research</i> , 57(3), 201-220. Domínguez, M., Romera, R., Sánchez, E., Fita, L., Fernández, J., Jiménez-Guerrero, P., ... & Gaertner, M. Á. (2013). Present-climate precipitation and temperature extremes over Spain from a set of high resolution RCMs. <i>Climate research</i> , 58(2), 149-164.

González-Alemán, J J, Gaertner, M. A., Sánchez, E., & Romera, R. (2018). Subtropical cyclones near-term projections from an ensemble of regional climate models over the northeastern Atlantic basin. *International Journal of Climatology*, 38, e454-e465.

Table 33:ROM simulations – North Atlantic and Mediterranean domain

Variable (can be generic, e.g. all atmospheric fields; marine hydrodynamics)
All atmospheric and oceanographic fields
Domain
Macaronesian, Caribbean and Mediterranean
Source (project, initiative, etc...)
Simulations performed by Alfred Wegener Institute (Germany)
Period : <i>Evaluation, Historical/Control, Scenario</i> (specify which runs are available with the spatial resolution) Evaluation (1980-2012); Historical/Control (1950-2005); Scenario (2006-2099) for RCP8.5 Spatial resolution: 25 km
Historical, Control and Scenario with coupled ocean- atmosphere models: <u>Coupled model simulations with the regionally coupled atmosphere-ocean-sea ice-marine biogeochemistry model ROM</u>
Data Availability: <i>public database</i> (specify address), <i>on-demand</i> (specify contact)
On demand. Contact: Miguel.Gaertner@uclm.es
More Information
Sein, D. V., Mikolajewicz, U., Gröger, M., Fast, I., Cabos, W., Pinto, J. G., ... & Jacob, D. (2015). Regionally coupled atmosphere- ocean- sea ice- marine biogeochemistry model ROM : 1. Description and validation. <i>Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems</i> , 7(1), 268-304.

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